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МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЮ УРОВНЯ РАЗВИТИЯ СИСТЕМЫ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ НА ПРОТЯЖЕНИИ ВСЕЙ ЖИЗНИ С УЧЕТОМ РЕГИОНАЛЬНОГО АСПЕКТА

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METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO DETERMINING THE LEVEL OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM THROUGHOUT THE LIFETIME, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE REGIONAL ASPECT

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Аннотация

В статье проведено оценку методических подходов к определению уровня развития системы образования на протяжении всей жизни с учетом регионального аспекта. Определены особенности образования с учетом специфики регионов, проанализированы имеющиеся статистические данные Латвии, предложен для расчета индекса регионального развития системы образования на протяжении всей жизни. Разработанная методика может быть использована латвийскими высшими учебными заведениями при практической работе.

Abstract

The article assesses methodological approaches to determining the level of development of the education system throughout life, taking into account the regional aspect. The features of education are determined taking into account the specifics of the regions, the available statistical data of Latvia are analyzed, and it is proposed to calculate the index of regional development of the education system throughout life. The developed methodology can be used by Latvian higher education institutions in practical work.

Ключевые слова: высшее образование, обучение, непрерывность, региональность.

Keywords: higher education, training, continuity, regionality.

One of the important prerequisites for the development of a competitive and innovative economy focused on "smart" and sustainable growth is the development of a system of education throughout life (SEL), which should become a strategic benchmark not only at the state, but also at the local levels. To do this, it is necessary to develop an effective financial support mechanism, which is taken into account in state and regional development strategies and plans. It should be noted that according to foreign experience, there is a tendency to identify individual administrative-territorial units as "learning regions". This practice is widespread among many countries of the European Union and is beginning to be introduced in other countries. This concept became widespread in the mid-90s of the last century thanks to the work of individual scientists. The Florida R. article noted: "... the regions themselves are becoming focal points for knowledge creation and learning in the new age of capitalism", and their main goal is "... to provide a series of infrastructures that promote the dissemination of knowledge, ideas and learning" [1, P.527-536].

The scientist attributed to these infrastructures:

- "industrial infrastructure", which included a network of firms that create goods and services;

- "labor market infrastructure" supplying qualified workers;

- "management infrastructure", including norms, rules, standards and informal models of interaction between firms, as well as firms and government organizations;

- "physical and communication infrastructure" that provides the delivery of goods and services and communication with each other, and also facilitates and supports the constant exchange of information, electronic data exchange, and the like [1, P. 527-536].

Thus, in our opinion, the region should be considered as a certain production system of intersectoral relations that functions and develops due to the effective dissemination of information and knowledge. Asheim B. in his work "Industrial districts as "learning regions". A condition for prosperity" (1996) explores the relationship between the economic prosperity of regions and the ability of medium-sized enterprises to collectively learn. He derives the proposition that the networks that provide the learning process should be,

first of all, quasi-integrated, i.e. include interaction between firms at different levels [2, P. 71-101].

An equally important contribution to the concept of "learning regions" was made by Morgan K., who in his work *The learning region: institutions, innovation and regional renewal*. (1997) highlighted the idea of the "network paradigm" that "markets and "hierarchies" are not exhaustive organizational forms that mobilize resources for innovative and economic development", that is, the interaction of such spheres as the state and the market, private and public is necessary. In his research, social capital occupies a significant weight, because Morgan K. argues that "social capital is best developed at the regional level, which maintains the regularity of interaction ... the social capital fund is the main factor explaining the difference between economically successful regions and unsuccessful ones" [3, P. 101-127].

In these studies, we can see that the development of "learning regions" is possible only through the intersectoral interaction of various stakeholders on the terms of participation in the management and development of these regional systems, especially the educational component. Around the same time, active support for the idea of "learning regions" began at the level of international organizations. In particular, the European Commission introduced the *Towards a European Learning Society* project, the purpose of which was to study the characteristics of "learning regions" and further support them (including financial ones). The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has made a significant contribution to the definition of the main features of the "learning region" based on the experience of European countries, which is closely related to the concept of lifelong learning. Noteworthy are the conclusions of OECD experts on the issue of different levels of life expectancy in the "Learning Regions":

- firstly, although higher education contributes to the development of innovation in the region, secondary education forms the direct skills that are crucial for new industrial technologies and learning "by doing";
- secondly, a high level of education in itself does not contribute to economic growth, the ability to apply it in the production process is important, that is, the practical side of education and the promotion of creativity at all levels of education are emphasized;
- third, the extent to which individuals and organizations are able to absorb and apply knowledge and innovation is critical to their competitiveness in the knowledge economy;
- fourthly, to put innovation and training at the basis of their development.

First of all, they are characterized by the support of economic activity through various combinations of continuous learning, innovation and the creative use of information and communication technologies [4, P. 81-91].

Based on this, the concept of a "learning region" has become part of the regional strategy of many countries. For example, Austria, UK, Canada, Germany,

USA, Japan, etc. have state programs for the development of the adult education system through the implementation of the project "Learning region - learning society" [2,P.71-101.]. In particular, in Germany, the government program "Learning Regions - Stimulation of Networking" (2001-2008) was introduced with a total budget of 130 million euros. Funding was provided by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) with the participation of all federal states and the European Social Fund (ESF) [5, P. 103-125.]. Thus, the concept of a "learning region" permeates and complements the theory of regional development. The main hypothesis is that the competitiveness of any region is determined by its learning ability [6, P.24-39].

First of all, we will explore the existing methods in the world for assessing the level of development of the education system throughout life. An analysis of the available sources showed that they are usually based on four "pillars" of education, proposed in the report of the International Commission on Education of UNESCO by Jacques Delors in 1996, and which included blocks:

- the ability to learn (Learning to Know) - a combination of general fundamental education with the ability to deeply study individual subjects;
- the ability to work (Learning to Do) - obtaining not only professional skills, but also broader skills (to resolve difficult situations, work in a team, etc.);
- the ability to live together (Learning to Live Together) - the development of the ability to implement joint projects, resolve conflicts, respect pluralism, values, traditions, develop peace and mutual understanding in society;
- the ability to develop (Learning to Be) – the development of one’s own personality and responsibility, independence and one’s own judgments, including memory, the ability to reflect, physical abilities, communication skills, aesthetic education, etc.

These postulates allow us to consider the education system as a whole, combining formal, non-formal and information education that meets the requirements of the modern world. They are usually used as the basis for calculating indicators characterizing the level of development of life expectancy. One such metric is the Composite Learning Index (CLI), developed by the Canadian Council for Learning and used to analyze lifelong learning in more than sixty Canadian cities as part of the Learning Cities concept. This model measures the impact of life expectancy both on individuals, the community, and on the region and the country as a whole using 4 blocks, 17 indicators and 26 special measurement tools. An equally important factor in the calculation of this index is the measurement of the impact of learning on life on social (adult literacy, civil society participation, early childhood development, public health, environmental responsibility) and economic outcomes (average income, unemployment rate).

The schematic structure of the construction of this index is shown in Figure 1.

Fig.1 The structure of building the Composite Learning Index (CLI)

This index is based on statistical data on the development of life expectancy in Canadian cities, which makes it impossible to compare it with other countries in the world. In addition, the use of this technique in its pure form is also difficult due to the specifics of the indicators selected for calculating the CLI index (in particular: the number of people who communicate with representatives of other cultures on a regular basis, the average time to get to learning spaces, etc.).

The European Community has developed its own index - The European Lifelong Learning Index (ELLI), also based on the recommendations developed by UNESCO. It is based on the same 4 blocks characterizing LOS. In both the calculation of the CLI and ELLI, the underlying four blocks can be summarized as follows:

- the ability to learn is associated with the acquisition, processing and analysis of knowledge in formal educational institutions (schools, universities, etc.);
- the ability to work is considered inseparable from the formation of certain skills and professional skills, often associated with the place of work or formed with the assistance of employers;
- the ability to live together is associated with the socialization of the individual;
- information education, which can be obtained with family, friends, colleagues, etc.;
- the ability to develop is associated with the self-development of a person and his ability to independently accumulate and process information into knowledge.

The general scheme for constructing the ELLI index is presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Structural components of the European Lifelong Learning Index (ELLI)

Let us characterize the main socio-economic results in more detail.

- Economic results:
 - 1) income (average net income; GNP per capita);
 - 2) productivity (labor productivity per employee);
 - 3) employment (employment rate; unemployment rate);
- Social outcomes:
 - 1) health (feeling, lifestyle and habits, life expectancy at birth);

- 2) life satisfaction or happiness level (including life satisfaction, happiness level, job satisfaction, home satisfaction);
- 3) social cohesion and democracy (long-term unemployment rate; Gini coefficient, poverty status in the EU; satisfaction with the level of democracy, the last elections, trust in political institutions);
- 4) sustainability (environmental performance index).

According to the available data from the ELLI index [7] countries such as Denmark, Sweden, the Netherlands, Finland had the highest indicators characterizing the overall development of LOS; the lowest rates are Romania, Bulgaria, Greece. These two groups are typical examples of the Scandinavian (social-democratic) and transitional models of states that support the development of education in different ways.

The CLI and ELLI indices reflect the overall picture of the development of lifelong learning in a particular country and are a positive factor for building a quality LLE. Based on the methodology of the UNESCO International Commission on Education, taking into account the specifics of the education system in Latvia, we propose a scientific and methodological approach to calculating the index of regional development of the LELS (Fig. 3).

After analyzing the available statistical data and their compliance with the above criteria, we propose to use the following indicators to calculate the regional development index of the life expectancy (RLLI). It should be noted that each block includes both quantitative (the number of general education, higher educational institutions, the number of students and students in them both at the stage of education and at the stage of graduation, the number of visits to museums, theaters, cinemas, libraries, etc.), and qualitative indicators, which are represented by financial indicators and are characterized by the level of financial security of this block (financing of basic and vocational education, public organizations providing educational services for the population of different ages, expenses for the spiritual and physical development of a person, etc.).

1. Formation of an array of statistical data for 2012–2022. what can affect lifelong learning in 4 regions of Latvia (Kurzeme, Zemgale, Vidzeme and Latgale) and Riga in five blocks:			
Block 1. (12 indicators) Ability to learn (I Know)	Block 2. (12 indicators) Ability to work (I Do)	Block 3. (8 indicators) Ability to work in a team and live together (I L/ve)	Block 4 (12 indicators) Ability to develop (I Be)
Block 5. Socio-economic indicators (SET) - 10 indicators: GNP per person, total income of the population, employment rate of the population: unemployment rate of the population, the number of crimes in society, average life expectancy: the level of development of the social environment: the comfort of life; general level of well-being; pleasure in work.			
2. Normalization and verification of the law of distribution of input data: the Harke-Beer criterion. skewness coefficient, kurtosis coefficient			
3. Checking Time Series for Anomalies and Eliminating Outliers: A Modified Irwin Method			
4. Factor analysis of blocks 1-5: selection of the most relevant indicators in each block using the method of principal components (PCA) using the rotation of factors using the “varimax” method, checking Kaizar and Cattell criteria			
5. Correlation analysis by blocks and cross-correlation analysis of indicators			
I Know (4 indicators): number of colleges (x_5) number of university students (x_8) graduation of university students (x_{10}) amount of public spending on formal education (x_{10})		I Live (5 indicators): number of members of public organizations (x_{26}); number of rallies, demonstrations (x_{27}); volume of state financing of public organizations (x_{30}); the amount of funding for public organizations from other sources (x_{31}); spending by public organizations on educational projects (x_{32})	
I Do (5 indicators): graduation of college students (x_{13}); the number of graduates who, simultaneously with the educational and qualification level, received a working profession (x_{19}); the number of students aged 25 and over in colleges, technical schools. vocational schools and universities ($x_{22,23}$); the amount of public spending on vocational education (x_{24})		I Be (4 indicators): served the population with libraries (x_{33}); number of theater visits (x_{37}); annual circulation of newspapers (x_{39}); the amount of public spending on spiritual and physical development (x_{44})	
6. Econometric assessment of the model for each block in order to determine the weighting coefficients for variables, characterizing their dependence on the socio-economic result (Y)			
7. Model quality assessment: Farrar-Glober test for multicollinearity. Goldfeld-Quandt test for heteroscedasticity			
8. Calculation of indices for each block (I Know, I Do, I Live, I LBe)			
9. Calculation of the regional development index (RLLI)		$RLLI_{(i)} = \frac{\sum R^2 \times L(know, do, live, be)}{\sum R^2}$	

Fig. 3. Scientific and methodological approach to the calculation of the index of regional development of LELS (RLLI) for Latvia

For comparability of the input data, it is necessary to normalize them by taking a logarithm and normalize the law of their distribution using the following indicators [8]:

- asymmetry coefficient, which is an estimate of the standard deviation calculated on the basis of a biased estimate of the variance;
- coefficient of kurtosis, which determines the degree of sharpness of the peak of the distribution of a random variable;
- the Harke-Beer criterion, calculated on the basis of the two above indicators and allowing you to test the hypothesis about the normal distribution of the time series.

For the processing of statistical data and a general assessment of the regional development index of the LLLI (RLLI) for Latvia, we suggest using the STATA 11 software package, which allows you to automatically calculate and analyze a large amount of information in the form of panel data. That is why the verification of the normality of the law of distribution of input data should be carried out using a program module. To check the time series for anomaly and eliminate outliers, we propose to use the modified Irwin method, which allows you to compare neighboring values of the series based on the standard deviation of the sample series.

An important step in the proposed scientific and methodological approach is to conduct a factor analysis of socio-economic indicators in order to single out one common indicator. To do this, we propose to apply the method of principal components (PCA) - a multivariate statistical approach that groups variables into separate factors in order to reduce the dimension in a set of variables and / or turn related variables into significant and independent ones.

Thus, the importance of each block of the RLLI Regional Development Index (RLLI) is based on the established relationship between education dimensions and socio-economic indicators. This model allows you

to compare regions with each other and identify different levels of development: high, medium and low. The index of regional development of the LELS allows for a retrospective assessment and comparison of the state of development of the education system throughout life in different regions and to identify the main leaders and outsiders. The obtained calculations can be used as the basis for assessing the effectiveness of the use of financial resources for the development of lifelong life and the formation of regional strategies for financial support for the development of lifelong life.

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